

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF BIOANALYTICAL METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF ARGATROBAN IN HUMAN PLASMA BY LC-UV

Varsha Rajkumar Jamakhandi, M S Kalshetti

Department of Quality Assurance, College of Pharmacy, Solapur, Maharashtra, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/07/2018

Available online

31/08/2018

Keywords

Argatroban,
LC-UV,
Human Plasma,
Bioanalytical Method.

ABSTRACT

LC-UV method for quantification of Argatroban in human plasma has been developed and validated. Drug is extracted by protein precipitation technique using methanol. Separation has been performed on Phenomenex C8 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with Phenomenex Security Guard Cartridges C8 (4x3mm) using acetonitrile: methanol: water (33:17:50) as mobile phase at 1.0 ml/min flow rate at 259 nm. The calibration curve was linear over concentration range of 200-5000 ng/ml ($r^2=0.999$). Argatroban was eluted at 4.2 min. The method is sensitive, precise and accurate. The method can be used for estimation of Argatroban in human plasma.

Corresponding author

Varsha Rajkumar Jamakhandi

Department of Quality Assurance,
College of Pharmacy, Solapur, Maharashtra, India.
vjamakhand28@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Varsha Rajkumar Jamakhandi et al.** Development and Validation of Bioanalytical Method for Estimation of Argatroban in Human Plasma by LC-UV. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(08).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Drug development is the process of bringing a new pharmaceutical drug to the market once a lead compound has been identified through the process of drug discovery. It includes pre-clinical research, clinical study and regulatory approval to market the drug.¹

Measurement of drug concentrations in biological matrices (such as serum, plasma, blood, urine, and saliva) is an important aspect of drug development. Such data may be required to support applications for new active substances and generics as well as variations to authorized drug products.²

A bioanalytical method is a set of procedures involved in the collection, processing, storage, and analysis of a biological matrix for a chemical compound.³

Bioanalytical procedures, such as gas chromatography (GC); high-pressure liquid chromatography (LC); combined GC and LC mass spectrometric (MS) procedures, such as LC-MS, LC-MS-MS, GC-MS and GC-MS-MS and ligand binding assays (LBAs), and immunological and microbiological procedures are performed for the quantitative determination of drugs and/or metabolites, and therapeutic proteins in biological matrices.⁴

Bioanalytical method validation is the process used to establish that a quantitative method is suitable for biomedical applications.³

Selective, sensitive, and validated analytical methods for the quantitative evaluation of drugs and their metabolites (analytes) and biomarkers are critical for the successful conduct of nonclinical and/or biopharmaceutics and clinical pharmacology studies.⁴ Argatroban { 1-[5-[(aminoiminomethyl)amino]-1-oxo-2-[[[(1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-3-methyl-8-quinolinyl)sulphonyl]amino]pentyl]-4-methyl-2-piperidine carboxylic acid, monohydrate} is used as an anticoagulant for prophylaxis or treatment of thrombosis in patients with heparin induced thrombocytopenia (HIT/HITTS). It is also used in patients with or at risk for heparin induced thrombocytopenia undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). Argatroban is a direct Thrombin inhibitor.⁵ It is a synthetic nonpeptide compound which binds reversibly to the catalytic site of thrombin but not to the substrate recognition site. As such, it produces a rapid and short lasting antithrombin action.⁶ It does not require the co-factor antithrombin III for antithrombotic activity. It exerts its effects by inhibiting thrombin catalysed or induced reactions, including fibrin formation; activation of coagulation factors V, VIII, and XIII; activation of protein C; and platelet aggregation. Argatroban is highly selective for thrombin with an inhibitory constant (K_i) of 0.004 μ M. It is approved for use in India by the Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation. The Argatroban is available in injection form (50 mg in 50 ml single use vial). Its molecular formula is $C_{23}H_{36}N_6O_5S \cdot H_2O$ and the molecular weight is 526.66.⁵

Fig. 1 : Structure of Argatroban.

Literature survey revealed estimation of Argatroban by several techniques such as Quantification of Argatroban have been reported on UPLC-MS/MS, UPLC-ESI-MS/MS, simultaneous estimation of Edoxaban and Argatroban by first derivative spectroscopic method and by absorbance correction method. Development and validation of stability indicating reversed phase HPLC method for estimation of Edoxaban and Argatroban in synthetic mixture have also been developed.

In this present study an attempt was made to develop RP-HPLC method for estimation of Argatroban in human plasma with better sensitivity, precision and accuracy using C8 column and UV detector.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

Drug

Sr. No.	Drug sample	Supplier
1.	Argatroban	Aurobindo pharmaceutical limited, Hyderabad.

Chemicals

1.	Acetonitrile LiChrosolv®	Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
2.	Methanol LiChrosolv®	Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
3.	Methanol GR	Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
4.	Water LiChrosolv®	Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai

Human Plasma

Drug free EDTA human plasma was procured from Gopibai Damani Blood Bank, Solapur.

Equipments and Accessories.

1.	HPLC Software	Younglins Acme 9000
	4 Channel vacuum Degasser & Mixer	Autochro-3000
	Gradient Pump	SDV50A
	Injector	SP930D
	UV-VIS Detector	Rheodyne
2.	Column Luna 5 μ , C8 (150x4.6mm)	UV730D
3.	Security Guard Cartridges C8 (4x3mm)	Phenomenex, USA
4.	RC membrane 0.45 μ m 15mm Syringe Filters	Phenomenex, USA
5.	Nylon 6,6 membrane 0.45 μ m 47mm Filters	Phenomenex, USA
6.	All Glass Filter Holder- 47mm (1L flask, 300ml funnel)	Pall India Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
7.	Ultra sonicator	Borosil Glass works Ltd., Mumbai
8.	UV-VIS Double Beam Spectrophotometer 1800	Microclean-103
9.	Electronic Balance AY220	Shimadzu, Japan
10.	Infrared Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu, Japan
11.	Cool MicroCentrifuge	Thermo Scientific
12.	Micropipettes (5-50 μ l, 100-1000 μ l) Lab pipettes	REMI -120
13.	Refrigerator	Thermo scientific
		Godrej Pentacool

Table. 2.1 Glassware's and Apparatus.

Sr.No	Apparatus	Grade/class	Manufacturer/supplier
1.	Centrifuge Tubes	Appropriate volumes	Tarsons
2.	Glass beakers	Appropriate volumes	Borosil Glassworks ltd
3.	Glass bottles	Appropriate volumes	Borosil Glassworks ltd
4.	Volumetric flask	Appropriate volumes (Class A)	Borosil Glassworks ltd
5.	Microcentrifuge tube	1.5 ml	Tarsons

Methods

Preliminary Analysis of Drug

Description:

The sample of Argatroban was observed for its color and texture.

Solubility:

The solubility of Argatroban was checked in various solvents like methanol, acetonitrile and water.

IR spectra:

Argatroban was scanned in the region of 4000-400 cm^{-1} to obtain the IR spectrum of Argatroban.

Melting point:

Capillary filled with Argatroban was kept in melting point apparatus and the melting point was determined.

Selection of wavelength:

Solution in the mobile phase was scanned in the range of 200-400nm. It was observed that drug showed considerable absorbance at 259 nm.

High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method

Preparation of Standards and Quality Control Samples:

A stock solution of 0.5mg/ml of Argatroban was prepared in methanol. Standard working solutions for spiking (20, 50, 100, 200, 400, 500 μ g/ml) were prepared by dilution of stock solution with methanol. Plasma solution for calibration and quality control samples (200, 500, 1000, 2000, 2500, 4000, 5000 ng/ml) and 200 ng/ml (LQC), 2500 ng/ml (MQC) and 4000 ng/ml (HQC) were prepared by spiking 10 μ l of standard working solution in 990 μ l of plasma.

Sample preparation and extraction.

1000 μ l of methanol was added to plasma solution and vortexed for 5 min then the solution was centrifuged at 8°C, 15000rpm for 30 min. 20 μ l aliquot was injected into the HPLC system.

Selection of mobile phase:

Standard plasma solutions of Argatroban (5000 ng/ml) were injected into the HPLC system. Different mobile phase were optimized by several trials to improve the peak shape of analyte for achieving appreciable separation. The solution was analyzed using different combinations of Acetonitrile: methanol: water. The best signal for analyte was achieved by using acetonitrile: methanol, water (33:17:50).

Validation of RP-HPLC Method**Selectivity:**

Blank plasma and LLOQ were injected separately and chromatograms were recorded.

Calibration/Standard curve:

On spiking plasma samples with seven non-zero calibration working solutions covering the total range of quantification (200-5000 ng/ml concentration in plasma) along with blank samples. The calibration curve was generated by plotting the peak area of analyte vs. concentration of analyte on linear regression method following the equation $y=0.031x+1.790$ where y denotes analyte area and x denotes concentration of analyte. The LLOQ as the lowest concentration yielding a signal to noise ratio of at least 5 with a coefficient of variation (CV) <20% and accuracy of 80-120%. The acceptance criteria for other standard concentration were within a 15% deviation from the nominal values.

Precision and accuracy

Both repeatability (within –run and between- run) were determined by replicate analysis of 5 sets of quality control samples that were spiked with 3 different QC concentrations. The precision was determined in the term of coefficient of variation (CV %) and accuracy was expressed as the absolute percent bias APB (%). The acceptance criteria should not exceed 15% (for LLOQ not exceed 20%).

Recovery:

Recovery tests were performed in replicate at three different quality control samples (1000, 2500 and 4000 ng/ml). Recovery was calculated by comparing the responses of plasma quality control samples spiked with analyte with response of analyte in equivalent to methanolic solution.

Stability:

Drug stability in a biological fluid is a function of the storage conditions, the chemical properties of the drug, the matrix, and the container system. Stability procedures should evaluate the stability of the analytes during sample collection and handling, after long-term (frozen at the intended storage temperature) and short-term (bench top, room temperature) storage conditions.

Freeze and Thaw stability:

Freeze thaw stability of the spiked quality control samples was determined after three freeze thaw cycles. Stability was assessed by comparing them against the freshly spiked quality control samples.

Short-term temperature stability:

Short-term temperature stability of the spiked quality control samples was determined for a period of 4 hours stored at room temperature. Stability was assessed by comparing them against the freshly spiked quality control samples.

Long-term stability:

Long-term stability of the LQC and HQC was determined for a period of 5 days. Stability was assessed by comparing them against the freshly spiked quality control samples.

Stock solution stability:

Stock solution stability of the drug was determined for a period 5 days stored in refrigerator at 4⁰ C and then for 6 hrs at room temperature. Stability was assessed by comparing them against the freshly spiked quality control samples. The % mean stability for Argatroban were found to be 98.859 and 100.127% which is within the acceptance limit of 85.00-115 %.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Preliminary Analysis of Argatroban****Table.6.1 Observations and Results of Preliminary Analysis of Argatroban.**

Sr. No.	Tests	Observations
1.	Description	White, crystalline powder
2.	Solubility	It is soluble in methanol, sparingly soluble in acetonitrile and insoluble in water.
3.	IR spectra	Major peaks were found at 3430, 1685, 2948.
4.	Melting point	218 ⁰ C

Fig.6.1. IR Spectrum of Argatroban.

Table 6.2 : Functional groups detection by IR spectrum.

Wave no. (cm ⁻¹)	Functional groups
3430.68	-N-H
1685.83	-C=O
2948.58	-C-H

Preliminary analysis of Argatroban such as description, solubility, IR spectrum and melting point confirms the identification of Argatroban.

RP-HPLC Method for Argatroban

Selection of wavelength

Fig 6.2 UV spectrum of Argatroban between 200-400nm in mobile phase.

Argatroban showed the absorbance at 259nm. Hence, HPLC analysis was carried out at 259nm.

Selection of Mobile phase

Table 6.3 Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions.

Column	Mobile phase	Retention time (min)	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
C ₁₈	50:00:50	2.3	4413.5	0.7930	3.8016
C ₁₈	37:30:33	3.15	2459.8	1.0219	1.3191
C ₁₈	40:20:40	3.1667	2459	1.0495	7.4989
C ₈	35:20:45	3.6167	2373.1	0.8515	8.0674
C ₈	33:20:47	4.0333	2194.5	0.8683	7.3798
C ₈	33:17:50	4.25	2184.6	0.8859	0.5858

(C8 Column, at 1ml/min flow rate, detection wavelength is 259nm, mobile phase ratio containing acetonitrile: methanol: water = 33:17:50 respectively)

After several permutations and combinations of mobile solvents with stationary phase C8, the method has been optimized i.e. Acetonitrile:methanol:water in the ratio of 33:17:50 respectively using C8 column which has given good resolution, capacity factor, etc. but most importantly Retention time which does not coincide with plasma.

Identification of Peak

Fig.6.3 Chromatogram of Blank plasma in optimized chromatographic conditions.

Fig .6.4 Method Development (33:17:50), Chromatogram of spiked plasma solution of Argatroban(200µg/ml).

Fig .6.5 Method Development (33:17:50), Chromatogram of spiked plasma (400µg/ml of Argatroban).

Fig.6.6 Method Development (33:17:50), overlain chromatograph of spiked plasma (400µg/ml of Argatroban) (-----)and methanolic solution of Argatroban.(-----)

**Validation of HPLC Method
Selectivity:**

Fig.6.7 Overlain chromatograph of spiked plasma (400µg/ml of Argatroban) (-----)and methanolic solution of Argatroban.(-----).

Results for specificity of biological matrix are listed below in table 6.4:

Table 6.4: Results for specificity of Argatroban.

DRUG			%
Sr.	LLOQ		Interference
No	Area	RT	
1	125.01	4.05	NIL
2	126.01	4.03	NIL
3	125.94	4	NIL

Response of interfering peaks at the retention time of drug should be $\leq 20.00\%$ of the response of respective LLOQ. For specificity at least 80.00% of the screened matrix lots with intended anticoagulant should be within the acceptance criteria.

Linearity, Accuracy, and Precision of Calibration Curve.

Fig.6.8 Overlain Chromatograms of spiked plasma solutions of Argatroban for calibration (20-500 µg/ml).

Table 6.5 Chromatographic response of Argatroban at linearity levels (200-5000 ng/ml).

Sr. no.	Concentration of Argatroban (ng/ml)	Area (mV)
1.	200	7.54
2.	500	16.99
3.	1000	34.21
4.	2000	64.03
5.	4000	126.01
6.	5000	157.95

Fig.6.9 Calibration curve of spiked plasma solutions of Argatroban.

Accuracy and Precision of Quality Control Samples

Table 6.6 Calculated Concentrations for Quality Control Samples.

QC ID	HQC	MQC	LQC	LLOQ QC
Nominal Concentration (ng/ml)	4000	2500	1000	200
P&A ID	Calculated Concentration (ng/ml)			
	3365.806	1903.225	1045.806	185.483
	3726.129	2245.483	1116.129	249.677
	3656.774	2453.225	1026.129	232.903
Mean	3582.903	2200.644	1062.688	222.6877
SD	191.1828	277.7281	47.31545	33.29388
% CV	5.3359	12.6203	4.452	14.95
% Mean Accuracy	89.572	88.025	106.2688	111.34
	4007.096	2472.258	1124.193	232.903
	4004.838	2502.580	1185.483	220.00
	3974.838	2508.709	1120.0	252.258
Mean	3995.591	2494.516	1143.225	235.0537
SD	18.00776	19.51779	36.6562	16.23618
%CV	0.45	0.782	3.206	6.907
% Mean Accuracy	99.889	99.780	114.3225	117.5265
	The % mean accuracy for all QC samples except of LLOQ QC should be in the range of 85.00-115.00%.			
Acceptance Criteria:	The % mean accuracy for LLOQ QC should be in the range of 80.00-120.00%. The % CV for all QC samples except of LLOQ QC should be within 15.00%. The % CV for LLOQ QC samples should be within 20.00%. Accept the P&A batch, when at least two third of all QC samples are within acceptance criteria.			

Within Batch Accuracy:

The within batch accuracy for all the low, middle and high quality control samples were ranged from 88.025 to 106.2688% which is within the acceptance limits of 85.00 to 115.00%. The within batch accuracy for all the LLOQ quality control sample was 111.34% which is within the acceptance limits of 80.00 to 120.00%.

Between Batch Accuracy:

The between batch accuracy for all the low, middle and high quality control samples were ranged from 88.025 to 114.3225% which is within the acceptance limits of 85.00 to 115.00%. The between batch accuracy for all the LLOQ quality control samples were ranged from 111.34 to 117.5265 % which is within the acceptance limits of 80.00 to 120.00%.

Within Batch Precision:

The within batch precision for all the low, middle and high quality control samples were ranged from 4.452 to 12.6203% which is within the acceptance limit of 15.00%. The within batch precision for all the LLOQ quality control sample was 14.95% which is within the acceptance limit of 20.00%.

Between Batch Precision:

The between batch precision for all the low, middle and high quality control samples were ranged from 0.45 to 12.6203% which is within the acceptance limit of 15.00%. The between batch precision for all the LLOQ quality control samples were ranged from 6.907 to 14.95 % which is within the acceptance limit of 20.00%.

Recovery**Table 6.7: Results for recovery of Argatroban.**

Replicate No.	HQC		MQC		LQC	
	Unextracted Area	Extracted Area	Unextracted Area	Extracted Area	Unextracted Area	Extracted Area
1	131.77	117.30	99.67	78.43	35.78	34.21
2	181.67	126.01	108.07	79.37	30.44	36.39
3	187.33	125.94	125.40	79.56	32.71	33.60
Mean	166.923	123.083	111.046	79.12	32.976	34.733
SD	30.57493	5.008636	13.12073	0.605062	2.679	1.4667
% CV	18.316	4.069	11.824	0.7647	8.1240	4.222
% Mean Recovery	73.736 %		71.249 %		94.941 %	

The % mean recovery for Argatroban in HQC, MQC and LQC was 73.736, 71.249, and 94.941% respectively.

Stability**A. Bench Top Stability:****Table 6.8: Results of bench top stability.**

Replicate No.	HQC		Sample ID	LQC	
	Comparison Sample	Stability sample		Comparison Sample	Stability sample
Nominal Concentration (4000 ng/ml)					
1	3365.806	4007.096	BT-LQC-001	1045.806	1124.193
2	3726.129	4004.838	BT-LQC-002	1116.129	1185.483
3	3656.774	3974.838	BT-LQC-003	1026.129	1120.00
Mean	3582.903	3995.591	Mean	1062.688	1143.225
SD	191.1828	18.00776	SD	47.31545	36.656
%CV	5.3359	0.45	%CV	4.452	3.206
%Mean Stability	89.671 %		%Mean Stability	92.955 %	
Nominal Concentration (1000 ng/ml)					
Calculated Concentration (ng/ml)					

Bench top stability of the spiked quality control samples was determined for 06 hours at ambient temperature. The % accuracy for HQC and LQC was found to be 89.671 to 92.955% respectively, which is within the acceptance limits of 85.00 to 115.00%

Freeze and Thaw Stability*Freeze and Thaw Stability (Below -20±5°C)***Table 6.9: Results of freeze thaw stability at below (-20±5°C).**

HQC			LQC		
Nominal Concentration (4000 ng/ml)			Nominal Concentration (1000 ng/ml)		
Replicate No.	Comparison	Stability	Sample ID	Comparison	Stability
	Sample	sample	Sample ID	Sample	Sample
1	3702.03	4007.096	FT LQC-001	1028.1	1045.806
2	3700.98	4004.838	FT LQC-002	1020.32	1116.129
3	3694.02	3974.838	FT LQC-003	1013.02	1026.129
Mean	3699.01	3995.591	Mean	1020.48	1062.688
SD	4.353	18.007	SD	7.541	47.315
%CV	0.117	0.45	%CV	0.738	4.452
%Mean Accuracy	92.577 %		%Mean Accuracy	96.028 %	

Freeze and thaw stability of the spiked quality control samples was carried out for 3 cycles below - 20°C. The % accuracy for HQC and LQC was found to be 92.577 to 96.028 % respectively, which are within the acceptance limits of 85.00 to 115.00%

Short Term Stock Solution Stability (STSS):**Table 6.10: Short term Stock Solution Stability for Drug.**

Drug		
Nominal Concentration (µg/ml)		
Replicate	5	5
No.	Peak Area	
	Comparison	Stability
1.	83.4	90.05
2.	82.9	88.06
3.	80.03	82.03
Mean	82.11	86.71
SD	1.818	4.176
% CV	2.214	4.816
% Mean Stability	94.694 %	

Short term stock solution stability for Drug at concentration 1mg/mL was determined by using aqueous standard approximately equivalent to SS STD 6 concentration (5µg/ml) after the storage for 06 hr at ambient temperature. Stability was assessed by comparing against the freshly prepared Drug stock solutions which were diluted approximately equivalent to SS STD 6 concentration (5µg/ml). The % mean stability for 07 hours 45 minutes at ambient temperature was found as 94.694% for Drug (Argatroban) which is within the acceptance limits of 90.00 to 110.00%. The % CV for stability samples was found as 4.816 % for Drug. The % CV for comparison samples was found as 2.214 % for Drug which is within the acceptance limits of 15.00%.

System Suitability Testing

Table.6.11: Results of System Suitability Parameters.

Analyte	Retention Time (min)	Tailing	Theoretical Plates (N)	Resolution (R)
		Factor (T)		
Argatroban Required	4.25	0.8859	2184.6	9.5858
limits	--	T < 2	N > 2000	R > 2

Study of resolution, tailing factor and capacity factor shows system is suitable for this method.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Results	FDA Limits
1.	System Suitability	N= 2184.6, Tailing factor=0.8859	--
2.	Calibration Curve	Linearity Range of Drug Correlation Coefficient of Drug	20-500µg/ml 0.999
	Accuracy of Drug	88.025-114.35%	85-115%
3.	Results	Precision of Drug(%CV)	0.45-12.6203% ± 15%
	Quality Control	Within Batch Accuracy of Drug Between Batch Accuracy of Drug	88.025-106.268% 88.025-14.3225%
	Results	Within Batch Precision of Drug Between Batch Precision of Drug	4.452-12.6203% ± 15% 0.45-12.6203%
4.	Selectivity	Specificity	No Interferences
5.	Recovery	% Recovery	-
		Drug	HQC
			73.736 %
			MQC
			71.249 %
			LQC
			94.941 %
		HQC	LQC
	Stability	Bench Top (06:00Hrs)	
6			89.671% 92.955% ± 15%
		FT(20±)	92.577 % 96.028%

CONCLUSION

In the present work, sensitive, specific, precise and accurate bioanalytical method for Argatroban in human plasma has been developed and validated with a larger calibration curve range (i.e. 200-5000 ng/ml) using high performance liquid chromatography which can be used for routine drug analysis and bioanalysis.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I, the author express my sincere gratitude to D.S.T.S. Mandal's College of Pharmacy, Solapur and the Principal of this college, Mr. R.Y. Patil for providing me the facilities required for the research work. I am grateful to Dr. M. S. Kalshetti, HOD, Department of Quality Assurance, D.S.T.S. Mandal's College of Pharmacy, Solapur for his meticulous guidance for the research work.

ABBREVIATIONS

Cm	: centimeter
µg	: microgram
ng	: nanogram
r	: correlation coefficient
UV	: ultraviolet
%	: percentage
LOD	: Limit of detection
LOQ	: Limit of quantification

REFERENCES

1. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Drug_development [Last accessed on 30 Jan 2018]
2. European Medicines Agency Science Medicines Health Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP). Guideline on Bioanalytical Method Validation. 1 February 2012.
3. Lalit V Sonawane, Bhagwat N Poul, Sharad V Usnale, Pradeepkumar V Waghmare and Laxman H Surwase. Bioanalytical method validation and its pharmaceutical applications – A review. *Pharmaceutica Analytica Acta*. 2014; 5(3): 1-7.
4. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services Food and Drug Administration Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER) Center for Veterinary Medicine (CVM) Biopharmaceutics. Guidance for Industry. Bioanalytical Method Validation. September 2013.
5. CDER. Application number 022434 Orig 1s000. Clinical pharmacology and biopharmaceutics review(s). Jan 2011.
6. K. D. Tripathi. *Essentials of Medical Pharmacology*. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers (P) Ltd. 2013; 620.
7. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/argatroban#section=Top> [Last accessed on 30 Jan 2018]
8. <https://www.rxlist.com/argatroban-drug.htm>[Last accessed on 30 Jan 2018]
9. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Argatroban>[Last accessed on 30 Jan 2018]
10. <https://www.medicinenet.com/argatroban-injectable/article.htm>[Last accessed on 30 Jan 2018]
11. Jeanne M Rhea, Marion L Snyder, Anne M Winkler, Charbel Abou-Diwan, Corinne R Fantz, James C Ritche, Fania Szlam, Kenichi A Tanaka, Ross J Molinaro. Development of a fast and simple liquid chromatography –tandem-mass spectrometry method for the quantitation of Argatroban in patient plasma samples. 2012; 893-894; 168-172.
12. Ross J Molinaro, Quantitation of Argatroban in plasma using liquid chromatography electrospray tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-ESI-MS/MS). *Methods in molecular biology book series*. 2010; 603.
13. Divya Patel, Hasumati A Raj, Vineet C Jain, First derivative spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of Edaravone and Argatroban in synthetic mixture ,*Asian pharma press*, Jan 2015.
14. Divya A Patel, Hasumati A Raj, Vineet C Jain. Absorbance correction method for simultaneous estimation of Edaravone and Argatroban in synthetic mixture, *Asian pharma press*. 2015; 5(1): 41-48.
15. Divya Patel, Development and validation of stability indicating Reversed Phase HPLC method for estimation of Edaravone and Argatroban in synthetic mixture. *International Journal of Applied Medical Sciences*. 2015; 1(1): 51-69.

54878478451180706

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

